

"Elutriating therapeutic prospective of natural pharmacological agents of Renatus Nova"

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Abstract

Poly-herbal formulations have shaken some most fruitful trees, herb-herb combinations are being used worldwide for various diseases and illness which are life threatening. Several, researchers, scholars and medicinal practitioners believe synergistic involvements of herbs and trees targets therapeutics of various diseases in innumerable ways. This review paper discusses twelve very essential ingredients used in agglomerated formulation named "Renatus Nova". Past year of Researches have been explored and scrutinised for herbs targeting antidiabetic, antioxidant, antimicrobial, anti mitotic, antiinfective, antiangiogenic, anticarcinogenic activities. The ingredients viz *Garcinia mangostana*, *Eleutherococcus senticosus*, *Boerhavia diffusa*, *Chlorophytum borivilianum*, *Sambucus nigra*, *Vaccinium myrtillus*, *Withania somnifera*, *Moringa oleifera*, *Asparagus racemosus*, *Ginkgo biloba*, *Tribulus terrestris*, and *Rubia cordifolia* are detailed in the present review proclaiming their life saving properties. Medicinal herbs are active in effecting disease treatments by the presence of their unique phytoconstituents in suitable amounts, any formulation of drug requires thorough study on phytoconstituents this review will act as platform for understanding role of analytes in drug synthesis.

Keyword : Medicinal herbs, Nutraceuticals, Nanomaterials, Therapeutics, Renatus Nova,

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Introduction

Ever since ancient times, in search for rescue for their disease, the people looked for drugs in nature. The beginnings of the medicinal plants' use were instinctive, as is the case with animals. In view of the fact that at the time there was not sufficient information either concerning the reasons for the illnesses or concerning which plant and how it could be utilized as a cure, everything was based on experience. In time,

the reasons for the usage of specific medicinal plants for treatment of certain diseases were being discovered; thus, the medicinal plants' usage gradually abandoned the empiric framework and became founded on explicatory facts. Until the advent of iatrochemistry in 16th century, plants had been the source of treatment and prophylaxis. Nonetheless, the decreasing efficacy of synthetic drugs and the

increasing contraindications of their usage make the usage of natural drugs topical again. Healing with medicinal plants is as old as mankind itself. The connection between man and his search for drugs in nature dates from the far past, of which there is ample evidence from various sources: written documents, preserved monuments, and even original plant medicines. Awareness of medicinal plants usage is a result of the many years of struggles against illnesses due to which man learned to pursue drugs in barks, seeds, fruit bodies, and other parts of the plants. Contemporary science has acknowledged their active action, and it has included in modern pharmacotherapy a range of drugs of plant origin, known by ancient civilizations and used throughout the millennia. The knowledge of the development of ideas related to the usage of medicinal plants as well as the evolution of awareness has increased the ability of pharmacists and physicians to respond to the challenges that have emerged with the spreading of professional services in facilitation of man's life. This review paper discusses twelve very essential ingredients used in agglomerated formulation named "Renatus Nova". Past years of Researches have been explored and scrutinised for herbs targeting antidiabetic, antioxidant, antimicrobial, anti mitotic, antiinfective, antiangiogenic, anti-carcinogenic activities. The ingredients viz *Garcinia mangostana*, *Eleutherococcus senticosus*, *Boerhaviadiffusa*, *Chlorophytum borivilianum*, *Sambucus nigra*, *Vaccinium myrtillus*, *Withaniasomnifera*, *Moringa oleifera*, *Asparagus racemosus*, *Gingko biloba*, *Tribulus terrestris*, and *Rubia cordifolia*. are detailed in the present review proclaiming their life saving properties. The key search word implemented

Nutraceuticals in given plants, Therapeutic benefits, strongevity and Immuno enhancers. Databases that were explored are Scopus, PubMed, NIHL pharamaceutics, Web of Science, Google scholar etc.

Garcinia mangosteen

Garcinia mangosteen has been regarded as one amongst the tastiest Tropical fruits and hence named "queen". Medicinal History of *Garcinia mangosteen* dates back to centuries for the treatment of ailments related to skin [1], subtle healing of wounds [2], Dysentery caused by Amoeba[3]. Studies of mangosteen's pharmacological has started since 1990's. Mangosteen is an important medicinal plant in the family of Clusiaceae. In the recent history, this plant is reported for various medicinal properties [4].

Nutritional and medicinal properties of *Garcinia mangosteen* Linn. Submitted to the fact of presence of metabolites such as prenylated and oxygenated xanthenes [5].

Various health-promoting activities of Xanthenes in the pericarp of Mangosteen fruit have been described by various researchers using different cellular models. The pericarp of GML is a source of xanthenes and other bioactive substances. Prenylated xanthenes isolated from GML have been extensively studied; some members of these compounds possess antioxidant, antitumoral, antiallergic, anti-inflammatory, antibacterial, antifungal and antiviral properties. Xanthenes have been isolated from pericarp, whole fruit, heartwood, and leaves. The most studied xanthenes are alpha-, beta-, and gamma-mangostins, gartinone E, 8-deoxygartanin, and gartinan.

Some of the therapeutic and medicinal potentials are mentioned below.

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Antibacterial Activity:

Tran *et al.* stated that γ -mangostin, garcinone D, mangostanin, α -mangostin, demethylcalabaxanthone have the strong inhibitory effect on Mycobacterium tuberculosis [21]. α -mangostin has antimicrobial activity against vancomycin-resistant Enterococci (VRE) and methicillin-resistant Staphylococcus aureus (MRSA) [6]. Reported by Voravuthikunchai and Kitpipit, the ethanol extract from mangosteen has an antimicrobial activity against methicillin resistant *Staphylococcus aureus*. Furthermore, Chomnawang *et al.* found that the crude extract of mangosteen can inhibit the growth of Propionibacterium acnes and *Staphylococcus epidermidis*. While, Hasegawa *et al.* reported that α -mangostin has also demonstrated an inhibitory effect against *Helicobacter pylori* [7].

Antifungal Activity:

Soares *et al.*, reveal that antifungal activity against tinea species, such as Trichophyton rudrum, Trichophyton mentagrophyte, and

Microsporiumgypseum [8]. While, Ibrahim *et al.* presented that xanthenes and α -mangostin are provenly tested for antifungal activity against three fungi, *Fusarium oxysporumvasinfectum*, *Alternaria tenuis*, and *Dreschleraoryzae* [9].

Antidiabetic and Anti hyperglycemic activity

Several studies showed the antihyperglycemic and antidiabetic activity of mangosteen. Husen *et al.* stated that the extract of mangosteen's pericarp has been proven to be effective for decreasing the fasting blood cholesterol level and lipid peroxidation in the type-2 diabetic mice [10]. In addition, Husen *et al.* also tested the antioxidant and antidiabetic activity from the extract of mangosteen's pericarp in the streptozotocin-induced diabetic mice. Moreover, Ansori *et al.* demonstrated the renoprotective effect from the extract of mangosteen's pericarp in the streptozotocin-induced diabetic mice [11]. Furthermore, Husen *et al.* reported an antioxidant activity assay of the alpha-mangostin for amelioration of kidney's structure and function in the diabetic

mice. Moreover, Husenet .also mentioned that the hepatoprotective effect of γ -mangostin for amelioration of the impaired liver's structure and function in the streptozotocin-induced diabetic mice.

Analgesic Activity: Cui et al. revealed that CEM and mangostins possess the potent peripheral and central antinociceptive effects in mice and suggested that xanthenes may be developed as the novel analgesics and anti-inflammatory drugs .

Antiviral Activity: α -Mangostin and γ -mangostin from mangosteen inhibited HIV-1 with IC50 values of 5.1 and 4.8 μ M, respectively [6]. Furthermore, Vlietinck et al. discovered that the role of α -mangostin as a non-competitive inhibitor of HIV-1 protease by inhibiting the HIV virus replication cycle [9].

Antiparasitic and Antihelmintic Activities: α -Mangostin and β -mangostin were reported to be inhibitory for the growth of *Plasmodium falciparum* clone D6. Several modified derivatives were prepared based on the skeleton of α -mangostin. Among these compounds, xanthone derivatives with alkylamine groups exhibits the most potent inhibitory activity against *P. falciparum* in an in vitro assay [10].

Nanotechnology and *Garcinia mangosteen*

The medicinal values of silver, gold, selenium ions reduction and stabilization by combining them with biomolecules, such as proteins, amino acids, enzymes, polysaccharides, alkaloids, tannins, phenolics, saponins, and vitamins, which already exist in the plant extracts, have medicinal value There is increasing interest in the using of nanotechnology for biomedical purposes could form the bulk of future treatment strategies for

different diseases. Furthermore,, found that Ag-NPs have anti-inflammatory effects by inhibiting metabolic activity through impairing mitochondrial function via oxidative stress. The quality of the mangosteen peel extract quality is dependent upon its antioxidative performance as well as the environmental and technological factors affecting these activities..

Siberian ginseng

The roots of Asian ginseng (*Panax ginseng* C. A. Meyer) have long been one of the most common components of general tonics employed in traditional herbal medicines throughout Asia due to their putative benefits in general health promotion, vitality, stamina, restoration of homeostasis, chemoprevention, wound healing, longevity, and other indications [11].

While each ginseng species exhibits several different mechanisms of action potentially related to health promotion and disease prevention, there is a need to better characterise their relative antioxidant capacity as reactive oxygen, nitrogen, and halide reactive species ("free radicals") contribute to the pathogenesis of age-related chronic diseases, including atherosclerosis, cancer, and neurodegenerative conditions. Indeed, a growing body of evidence suggests the medicinal efficacy of the different ginseng species is mediated via their antioxidant actions [12] e.g., inhibiting lipid peroxidation and oxidative injury to DNA [13]. Several reports indicate the different ginseng species are effective in scavenging free radicals, inducing antioxidant enzyme activity, and stimulating glutathione synthesis [14].

Siberian ginseng

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Anti-Diabetic Property

Ginseng has shown affect on metabolic disorders by modulating the HPA axis, the core of the hormonal regulation system. Diabetes mellitus is one of the most prevalent metabolic diseases in modern societies. Stress can affect metabolism and cause chronic hyperglycemia. When an organism encounters an emergency, the autonomic nervous system reacts with the fight or flight response, which includes energy mobilization. Thus, the stress response involves the actions of a variety of hormones that raise the blood glucose concentration. Some patients with Diabetes mellitus show increased insulin resistance and consequently have a reduced response to insulin. When stressful situations develop where energy is needed, the body cells

of these Ginseng is also effective in regulating the adaptive immune response because of its effects on lymphocytes. First, ginseng activates the MAP kinase pathway by activating various transcription factors, thus functioning as an anti-inflammatory agent. In addition to inhibiting the CD40 signaling that stimulates the interaction between antigen-presenting cells and T lymphocytes, ginseng can exert chronic anti-inflammatory and antiallergic effects [15]. As such, ginseng is effective for the treatment of allergic asthma caused by problems with the Th2-predominant T cell response. Asthma is an airway inflammation that can narrow the respiratory tract, causing shortness of breath and coughing. This can develop into a serious inflammatory condition that can be fatal [16].

The prevalence of asthma is increasing worldwide, and it is also closely associated with anxiety and depression, which are caused by stress [17].

Antioxidant, Total Phenolic content, Total Flavonoid content and their benefits

The pharmacological activity of natural products is very regularly believed to be the result of the combined of constituents. The major compounds of *E. senticosus* are polyphenols. These compounds comprise-eleuthero sides, flavonoids and phenolic acids. The roots of *E. senticosus* are good resource of phenols, called as eleutherosides and flavonoids, triterpenic acids, phenolic acids and anthocyanins mainly eleutherosides B, E, E1 [18]. Shetty et al., analyzed the Total Phenol and Flavonoids content and antioxidant properties suggested that Siberian ginseng root is an abundant source of natural antioxidant activities. In addition, the presence of ursolic acid and sesquiterpene hydrocarbons in the root extract of Siberian ginseng shown the potential source as a crude drug and dietary health supplement. Further studies on the isolation and characterization of the root extract and toxicity should be tested to confirm the safety use [19].

Other health benefits

Cardiovascular health : Lee and Kim in a review mentioned to date, approximately 40 ginsenosides have been identified, and each has a different mechanism of action owing to the differences in chemical structure. This review aims to present comprehensive information on the traditional uses, phytochemistry, and pharmacology of ginseng, especially in the control of hypertension and cardiovascular function. In addition, the review also provides

an insight into the opportunities for future research and development on the biological activities of ginseng.

Antiviral & Anti cold Siberian ginseng was traditionally used to prevent colds and flu and to increase energy, longevity, and vitality. It is widely used in Russia as an "adaptogen." An adaptogen is a substance that is supposed to help the body better cope with either mental or physical stress [20].

Nanotechnology & Siberian ginseng

Wu et al., synthesized a cost-effective nanobased phyto drug to treat melanoma. Gold nanoparticles were biosynthesized with aqueous extract of *Siberian ginseng* as an organic reducing agent. The synthesized drug was characterized using various techniques and assessed for the anticancer property against murine melanoma B16 cells which is potent *in vitro* model resembles the human skin carcinoma condition [21].

***Boerhavia diffusa* L.**

The major active principle present in *B. diffusa* is alkaloidal in nature and known as boeravinone. Battery of bioactive phytochemicals are present in the various parts of the plant, which is responsible for number of pharmacological properties such as anti-inflammatory [21], antidiabetic [22], antioxidant [23], antistress [24], antimicrobial [25], or antibacterial or antiviral, antifungal [4], antinematodal [26], antifibrinolytic [27], antiurethritis [28], anticonvulsant [29], antihepatotoxic [30], diuretic [31], immunomodulatory [24], hepatoprotective [25], renoprotective or nephroprotective [26], laxative [27], adaptogenic [28], antimetastatic [29] and antihistaminic [30].

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Anti-inflammatory and Analgesic properties

Babita et al., mentioned in their work that all the parts of plants are useful in the treatment of pain ant in general, leaf juice in particular (Babita et al., 2011) [31]. Hiruma et al. Antioxidant activity Oxygen free radicals produced as a result of metabolic processes in our body, induce damage to biomembranes and genetic materials leading to many chronic degenerative diseases and aging (Juna Beegum et al., 2016) [36]2000) [32].

Anti-hepatotoxic Activity or Hepatoprotective and Cholerectic activity

Liver, a important vital organ of the body and first line of defence against xenobiotic attack. Hence, it is targeted by harmful and toxic effect of chemicals. It helps to combat the body for

any onslaught. A good health is mirrored by good liver. Many workers evaluated and justify hepatoprotective potential of Boerhaaviadiffusa against different hepatic disorders and hepatotoxins (Shikha Mishra et al., 2014) [32].

Diuertic and Nephroprotective Activity Many research workers studied the effect of Boerhaaviadiffusa extract on kidney and are in agreement that it has diuretic effect. The diuretic activity was attributed to increased sodium excretion rate, presence of potassium, glucosides, ecdysone in various parts of plant. However, the maximum diuretic effect observed if roots are taken and as for as collection of season is concerned, maximum activity obtained in plants of rainy season .[33].

Adaptogenic and Antistress Activity The adaptogen refer to substances which increase "nonspecific" resistance to adverse influence to organism and stress. The adaptogenic substances restore, strengthen the normal body function compromised by stress as well as have a protective effect on health against varied environmental assaults and emotional conditions, in other words adaptogens useful during adrenal hyper stress and adrenal hypofatigue (Pranati Nayak and M Thirunavoukkrasu, 2016) [34].

Anticarcinogenic and Antiproliferative Activity *Boerhaviadiffusa* have shown cytotoxic and antiproliferative effect on various cell lines, like human cervical cancer HeLa cell line (Srivastava et al., 2009), mouse macrophage cells (RAW 264.7), human macrophage cells (U937), human monocytic cells (THP-1), mouse fibroblast cells (L929), human embryonic kidney cells (HeLa293), mouse liver cells (BNCLC.2), African green monkey kidney cell (COS-1), mouse lymphoma cells (EL-4), human erythroleukemia cells (K562), and human T cells (Mehrotra et al., 2002) [35].

Nano-technology and *Boerhaviadiffusa* L.

Jayadharani et al., used plant of *Boerhaviadiffusa* L. as a catalyst in the synthesis of silver nano - particles [36].

Bairwa et al., found out that the 70% ethanol extract was used extricate nano retinoids, and all isolated nanorotenoids were evaluated for their COX-1 and COX-2 inhibitory activities.

Among the rotenoids tested, compound 7 showed the most potent COX-1 and COX-2 inhibition, with IC_{50} values of 21.7 ± 0.5 and $25.5 \pm 0.6 \mu M$, respectively. Boeravinone B (6) exhibited significant anti-inflammatory activity (56.6% at 50 mg/kg) when evaluated in an in vivo carrageenan-induced rat paw model [37]. Hence it can be concluded that nutraceuticals such as retinoids are more effective in therapeutics and needs exploration.

Chlorophytum borivilianum

Safed Musli are known to boost energy levels, relieve pre-natal and post-natal problems and act as a remedy for arthritis. Its purported use as an aphrodisiac agent may be a more recent discovery. Some online sources claim that the active components in the extract may include 25 different alkaloids, vitamins and minerals. These substances may be the underlying reason why it has been linked to increase sex drive and stamina. The mechanism may act by elevating male testosterone levels, which has been shown to influence virility and sex drive in men. We find in the male sexual enhancement category, the more promising supplements are those that contain a potent blend of proven ingredients, rather than just relying on a single ingredient. People may wish to consider some of the following substances: Tribulus Terrestris, Epimedium, Yohimbe Extract, MuiraPuama, Panax Ginseng, Catuaba Bark Extract and Damiana.

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Aphrodisiac activity: Singh et al., mentioned that the aqueous extract of dried roots of *C. borivillianum* reported to have a potent aphrodisiac and spermatogenic potential. To evaluate this effect, male wistar albino rats were orally treated with the dose of 125 and 250 mg/kg/day, their sexual behaviour was monitored 3 hr later using a receptive female [38].

Antidiabetic activity

Gayathri et al., found in their work that supplementation of the tuber to Type 2 diabetics showed a substantial decrease in blood glucose, total, LDL, VLDL cholesterol, triglyceride level and a significant ($p < 0.05$) improvement in HDL cholesterol level. The Analysis of Variance clearly indicated that the treatment adopted for Group III subjects (Diabetics + *C. borivillianum*) was on par with Group IV subjects (Diabetics + glibenclamide).

Improved antioxidant status was observed in the controls supplemented with *C. borivillianum*. Before the treatment diabetics exhibited very low levels of enzymic and nonenzymic antioxidants, but after treatment, these levels significantly increased in the diabetics administered with the tuber of *Chlorophytum borivillianum*. It was found to be much higher than that of the diabetics taking glibenclamide [39].

Other medicinal importance of *Chlorophytum borivillianum*

The powdered root of safedmusli is taken in a number of ways on the subcontinent and in India it is one of the ingredients available for paan. It is also often fried in ghee (clarified butter) and chewed to relieve sore throats and mouth ulcers primarily, but of course is ingested and so helps with sexual vigor. Passion Rx potent aphrodisiac formula -- Medical Doctor

formulated for Female and Male Sexual Enhancement supplement. The roots of *Asparagus racemosus*, *Chlorophytum borivilianum*, and rhizomes of *Curculigoorchioides* are popular for their aphrodisiac and immunostimulatory properties. The herbs have been traditionally used as VajikaranRasayana herbs because of their

putative positive influence on sexual performance in humans [40].

Sambucus nigra

Elderberry has for a long time been used in folk medicine as a diaphoretic, antipyretic and diuretic agent. In recent years it was also found to have antibacterial, antiviral antidepressant and antitumour and hypoglycemic properties, and to reduce body fat and lipid concentration.

Sambucusnigra

Antioxidant Potential

Elderberry fruit is characterized by high antioxidant activity, which ranges from 82.08 to 89.25% of inhibition in relation to the DPPH radical. The antioxidant properties of elderberries are primarily attributable to the presence of phenolic compounds and depend largely on the chemical structure of molecules and composition of individual berries [41]. Anthocyanins significantly influence the antioxidant activity of elderberries. With the increase of anthocyanin concentration the antioxidant activity also increases, but only to a certain level above which this parameter starts to fall [42].

Antibacterial and antiviral properties

The antibacterial activity of elder flowers, berries and leaves (aqueous or ethanol extracts of freeze-dried elder concentrates) was studied against 13 nosocomial pathogens, including methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA), which is known as a clinically significant pathogen connected with infections of skin and soft tissue. Despite a 100-fold dilution, ethanol extracts of both elder flowers and berries exhibited inhibitory activity for most of the analysed bacteria, both Gram-positive, such as *Staphylococcus* sp. or *Bacillus cereus*, and Gram-negative, such as *Salmonella poona* or *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. Elderflower extracts displayed a higher antimicrobial efficacy and larger zones of inhibition against a broad range of bacteria, particularly MRSA (17 mm) or *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (9 mm), than other extracts. A ten-fold diluted aqueous extract of elder leaves showed moderate activity against the development of *Bacillus cereus* and *Serratia marcescens* (6 mm), but was not able to inhibit the growth of any crucial nosocomial pathogens [43].

Anti-diabetic Activity

Elder may be an effective traditional remedy for diabetes, and as such, it could be used as a dietary adjunct in diabetes treatment. It was found that water-soluble compounds included

in elder flowers were able to directly stimulate glucose metabolism and promote insulin secretion through clonal pancreatic β -cells. An extract of elder flowers (1 g/L) significantly increased glucose uptake, glucose oxidation and glycogenesis in vitro in mice abdominal muscles without added insulin [44].

Antibacterial Activity

Sambucus nigra fruit possesses antimicrobial activity against human pathogenic bacteria that cause infections of the upper respiratory tract. The addition of a standardized liquid extract of elderberry, at a concentration of 10%, to bacterial liquid cultures decreased the growth of Gram-positive bacteria strains of *Streptococcus pyogenes* and *Streptococcus* Group C and G, as well as Gram-negative bacteria *Branhamella catarrhalis*, by more than 70% compared to the control samples. A concentration of 20% of the elderberry extract inhibited the bacterial development by 99% [45].

Vaccinium myrtillus L.

Bilberry (*Vaccinium myrtillus* L.) is one of the richest natural sources of anthocyanins. These polyphenolic components give bilberry its blue/black color and high antioxidant content, and they are believed to be the key bioactives responsible for the many reported health benefits of bilberry and other berry fruits. Although bilberry is promoted most commonly for improving vision, it has been reported to lower blood glucose, to have anti-inflammatory and lipid-lowering effects, and to promote antioxidant defense and lower oxidative stress. Therefore, bilberry is of potential value in the treatment or prevention of conditions associated with inflammation, dyslipidemia, hyperglycemia or increased oxidative stress, cardiovascular disease (CVD), cancer, diabetes, and dementia and other age-related diseases. There are also reports that bilberry has antimicrobial activity.

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Antioxidant potential

Anthocyanins are potent antioxidants that scavenge radicals and chelate metal ions [46]. Many herbs and berries have powerful antioxidant properties, and these properties are thought to underlie many of the various health effects of herbs and berries.

In primary cultures of rat hepatocytes, it was found that bilberry extract protected cells against oxidative damage [47]. As described by [48], bilberry or anthocyanin extracts of bilberry protect rat liver microsomes against oxidative damage and apolipoprotein B against ultraviolet (UV)-induced oxidative fragmentation. Animal studies show conflicting results. In a rat study, no significant change of urinary 8-OHdG (also known as 8-oxodG, and a biomarker of oxidative stress; [49], was reported after 14 weeks of supplementation with an anthocyanin-rich extract from mixed berries including bilberry [50].

Anti- Cancer and Anti -Tumor properties

One in three people will receive a diagnosis of cancer at some point in their lives [51]. Treatment of cancer is harsh and often unsuccessful. Cancer is a disease caused by mutations in key genes controlling cell division and growth. Damage to DNA increases the likelihood of such mutations, and any bioactive food or component that is found to protect DNA from damaging agents, lower baseline DNA damage, or increase DNA repair is a potential cancer-preventing agent [52]. Although damage to DNA can be of many types and can result from many different processes and agents, oxidation-induced damage is thought to be a key factor. Chronic inflammation increases ROS load, and it is an important cancer risk factor [53].

Suiting Cardio Health

All over the world, CVD is a leading cause of death. Major risk factors of CVD include central obesity, diabetes, hypertension, elevated levels of lipids, and high levels of uric acid. Increased

oxidative stress may also contribute, and inflammation is a key factor. Atherosclerosis, the main underlying factor in CVD, is an inflammatory process associated with oxidative processes in and damage to the vascular endothelium [54]. Therefore, the anti-inflammatory and antioxidant effects of anthocyanins are of relevance to potential cardioprotective effects of bilberry and other berries. Antihypertensive, lipid-lowering, hypoglycemic, and antiobesity effects would also be cardio-protective [56].

Anti-Inflammatory Effects

Inflammation is a protective mechanism, but chronic inflammation increases oxidative stress and underlies many age-related diseases, including CVD and cancer [57]. Many studies suggest that anthocyanins, the predominant phenolic compounds found in bilberry, have anti-inflammatory effect [58]. Suggested mechanisms include inhibiting proteasome activity, which controls the degradation of cellular proteins [58], and inhibiting nuclear factor κ B (NF- κ B) activation, which controls expression of genes involved in the inflammatory response [59].

Anti-microbial Activity

Antimicrobial effects of herbs and natural products can be via inhibition of bacterial

binding (adhesion) to cell walls, direct antimicrobial killing, or by effects that potentiate antibiotics, as evidenced by lowered minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) of antibiotics in the presence of an herb compared to that of the antibiotic alone. Several natural products have been found to have antimicrobial effects [60] Activities has been found against *Salmonella* and *Staphylococcus aureus*[61], *V. macrocarpon* and *H. pylori* [62].

Withaniasomnifera

Withaniasomnifera has diverse phytochemical constituents, and is unique as it possesses steroidal alkaloids and lactones. *Withaniasomnifera* also possess novel biochemical molecules with potent pharmacological activities like withaferin, withanolides, and withanimades etc. To date, at least 12 alkaloids and 35 withanolides have been identified, and studied by scientists.[63]

Biological activities like antimicrobial, anticancer, anti-neurodegenerative and immunomodulator activity. Majority of these pharmacological functions are due to its different extract preparations and phytochemical constituents. Some of the remarkable clinical attributes are discussed below.

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Antimicrobial activity

In vitro studies have reported that dichloromethane and ethyl acetate extracts of *Withania somnifera* exhibits good bacteriocidal, and fungicidal activity against *Staphylococcus aureus* (SA), methicillin resistance *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA) and *Trichophyton mentagrophytes*. These extracts directly work through cytotoxicity leading to cell growth arrest [64].

Anti-cancer activity or Anti tumor Activity

Scholars have mentioned in their findings that *Withania somnifera* have controlling effect on azoxymethane induced colon cancer and immune dysfunction [65].

Immunomodulatory activity

Oral administration of 75% methanolic extract of ashwagandha significantly increases total leucocyte count in normal BALB/c mice and in mice with leucopenia induced by sub-lethal dose of gamma irradiation [65]. Ashwagandha extracts, coded as WST and WS2, were studied by a research group to investigate their immunomodulatory activities in validated experimental swiss albino mice models. Their study revealed *Withania somnifera* as an

important anti-allergic agent, the anti-allergic activity being more prominent with WS2 as compared to WST. WS2 extract has effect [66].

Withania somnifera and Nano- particles

Maheshwari et al., observed that *Withania somnifera* - *Eclipta prostrata* modified TiO₂ nanoparticles exhibit excellent anticancer activities among other bio modified and pure samples. The samples are then examined for their antibacterial activities against three Gram-negative bacterial strains namely, *Escherichia coli*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and two Gram-positive bacterial strains namely, *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Streptococcus mutans*. Among the modified and pure samples, *Withania somnifera* - *Eclipta prostrata* showed good antibacterial nature against Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria [67].

Moringa oleifera

Scientists have proven that leaves of *Moringa oleifera* are rich in minerals, vitamins and other essential phytochemicals. Extracts from the leaves are used to treat malnutrition, augment breast milk in lactating mothers. It is used as potential antioxidant, anticancer, anti-

inflammatory, antidiabetic and antimicrobial agent.

Analgesic and Anti-inflammatory

Almost every part of this "miracle tree" has been found to exhibit analgesic activity in different animal models. Extract of leaves, seeds, and bark showed significant analgesic activity in both central (hot plate method) and peripheral models (acetic acid-induced writhing method) in a dose-dependent manner, [68] and extracts of leaves exhibited analgesic potency similar to that of indomethacin [69] and antimigraine properties in a dose-dependent manner. [70] Topical application showed efficacy against multiple sclerosis-induced neuropathic pain. [71]

Anti-inflammatory activity of leaf extract has been observed in a carrageenan-induced paw edema model. [72] Extracts of bark showed anti-inflammatory activity comparable to diclofenac in the same model. Anti-inflammatory properties of root have also been reported. [73] Mechanism underlying the anti-inflammatory activity may be attributed to the regulation of neutrophils and c-Jun N-terminal kinase pathway. [74].

Antioxidant activity

MO fruits and leaves have antioxidant properties. Extract of leaf showed a concentration-dependent increase in glutathione level and a decrease in malondialdehyde level, fruit extract showed beneficial results in eliminating free radicals, extract of roots significantly reduced iron and FeSO₄-induced microsomal lipid peroxidation in a dose-dependent manner [75].

Effects on the reproductive system

Leaf extract showed a significant increase in the weight of testis, seminal vesicle, epididymis, and a higher score for epididymal maturity and lumen formation along with an increase in seminiferous tubule diameter (all doses) [76].

Ginkgo biloba-

Ginkgo is used as an herbal remedy to treat many conditions. It may be best known as a treatment for dementia, Alzheimer's disease, and fatigue. Other conditions it's used to treat are anxiety and depression, schizophrenia, insufficient blood flow to the brain, blood pressure problems, altitude sickness, erectile dysfunction, asthma, neuropathy, cancer, premenstrual syndrome, attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD), macular degeneration, etc.

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Anticancer Effects - Ahmed et al. investigated the effectiveness of GBE for the treatment of rats with hepatocellular carcinoma (HCC). GBE significantly enhanced the histological characteristics of liver tissue, decreasing the levels of alpha-fetoprotein (AFP), glypican-3 (GPC-3), and carcinoembryonic antigen (CEA) in HCC rats via the increased gene expression of inhibitor of growth (ING)-3 and the decreased gene expression of the transcription factor forkhead box protein 1 (FOXP1) in the liver. [77]

Antidementia Effects - Most EGb 761 clinical trials are targeted at enhancing cognition and memory, with some concentrating on dementia, particularly dementia presentations associated with the gradual loss of cognition and memory, including vascular dementia, Lewy body dementia, and frontotemporal dementia. Because EGb 761 can prevent amyloid production and toxicity, control excitotoxic

glutamatergic neurotransmission, and act as a radical scavenger, it could potentially be used to treat multiple dementia etiologies. [78]

Antidiabetic Effects - Several in vivo investigations have demonstrated that GBE has antidiabetic effects. Bilobalide, according to one study, shielded lipid cells against oxygen deficiency-induced insulin resistance and reduced inflammation by increasing adiponectin secretion, blocking the serine phosphorylation of insulin receptor substrate 1 (IRS-1) receptors in the insulin signaling cascade, lowering inflammatory adipokine production, and decreasing nuclear factor kappa B (NF- κ B)/c-Jun N-terminal kinase (JNK) activation. [79]

Antiobesity Effects - GBE administration was found to be beneficial for reducing body weight. Food consumption over a 24-hour period was measured by assessing the difference between the quantity provided and quantity remaining.

The gene expression levels of insulin receptor (IR), IL-10, and lipid receptor R1 (Adipo R1) and the phosphorylation of Akt all increased significantly, potentially stimulating the insulin signaling cascade. By contrast, TNF- α levels and NF- κ B p65 phosphorylation were reduced. The anti-inflammatory activities of GBE, which reduces TNF- α levels in retroperitoneal fat deposits, can mitigate the negative effects associated with excessive high-fat diet consumption. [80]

Antilipidemic Effect - Dyslipidemia is defined by high TG levels, low high-density lipoprotein cholesterol (HDL-C) levels, and increased low-density lipoprotein cholesterol (LDL-C) levels. In addition, hyperlipidemia has been associated with obesity and insulin resistance. In a separate study of male rabbits, *G. biloba* (10 mg/kg/day) treatment dramatically decreased plasma cholesterol and TG levels while significantly increasing HDL-C levels compared with the control group. Furthermore, in aortic tissue, *G. biloba* has been found to lower MDA levels while raising glutathione (GSH) levels. [81]

Treatment of Cardiovascular Diseases - The impacts of *G. biloba* seeds on the cholesterol metabolism were initially studied by Mahadevan et al., who studied the effects of the lipid metabolism and cardiovascular disease prevention mediated by various components of *G. biloba* seeds, including whole seeds, water-soluble fraction, and lipid-soluble fraction [82]. In vitro studies have shown that *G. biloba* seeds can impact the synthesis of apolipoprotein B and LDL receptor, modulating the blood cholesterol level of the liver. In vivo, whole seeds reduced hepatic cholesterol levels while increasing serum cholesterol levels. The lipid-soluble portion reduced hepatic cholesterol levels, whereas the water-soluble portion increased serum cholesterol levels, suggesting that lipid-soluble portion of *G. biloba* seeds could be used to lower the risks of heart disease. *Ginkgo* seed ethanol extract was shown to be beneficial in high-fat diet-fed mice. The ethanolic extract effectively prevented fat

accumulation and lowered the overall body weight in mice, associated with a substantial decrease in adipocyte size and epididymal adipose tissue weight compared with untreated animals suggesting that *Ginkgo* seed ethanol extract might reduce serum levels of HLD cholesterol. [83]

Antimicrobial Effects - Antimicrobial activity has been established for several components of *G. biloba* plants, including phenolic acids, polysaccharides, and proteins. Ginkgolic acids have been the subject of several experiments examining the antimicrobial functions of *G. biloba* seeds. Ginkgolic acids are fatty acids with the compositions C13:0, C15:0, C15:1, C17:1, and C17:2, and the antimicrobial activities of ginkgolic acids are aided by the presence of an alkyl side-chain. [84]

Anti-ageing effects - *G. biloba* leaf extract and aqueous *G. biloba* ethanol extract have been shown to display skin protective effects, and the molecular pathways involved have been studied using HaCaT keratinocytes, revealing antioxidant effects and antiaging results [85]. Many different GBEs have been shown to cause biphasic reactions in a wide variety of cell types. GBE applied as a topical formula achieved good skin penetration and retention, with beneficial effects for the skin, including protection from ultraviolet (UV) damage. [86]

Tribulus terrestris –

Over the years, people have taken tribulus in an attempt to enhance athletic performance, body building, and for a wide range of health issues that may include heart and circulatory conditions and sexual issues. Limited studies show it might be helpful in lessening symptoms of angina and in enhancing athletic performance. There have also been some studies that show some benefit to people with certain sexual problems and to those suffering from infertility. Evidence is lacking that shows benefits of tribulus for other health conditions. With a lack of research to draw on, it's not clear what a safe dosage is. Also, quality and active ingredients in supplements may vary widely from maker to maker. This makes it difficult to set a standard dose.

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Sexual disorders:-

Since long *T. terrestris* known for its aphrodisiac properties and as a traditional medicine for treating male infertility. [87] A formulation of the saponins from *T. terrestris* was developed for veterinary application and production in Bulgaria. [88] This formulation was effective in stimulating the sexual system (spermatogenesis, *libido sexualis*). Using *T. terrestris* extracts, an increase in sexual function in rats was demonstrated and attributed to an increase in testosterone, dihydrotestosterone, and dehydroepiandrosterone. [89]

Cardiac diseases:-

Research studies revealed that saponins of *T. terrestris* can play a role in dilating coronary artery and improving coronary circulation. The results of a clinical trial on 406 patients, when treated

with saponin of *T. terrestris* showed that the total efficacious rate of remission angina pectoris was 82.3% and the total effective rate of ECG improvement was 52.7% higher. Therefore, *T. terrestris* was recommended for treatment of angina pectoris. [90] Many research studies revealed that aqueous extract of *T. terrestris* fruits have some antihypertensive effect. [91]

Antimicrobial activity:

Antimicrobial activities of *T. terrestris* are reported to vary with the origin of the plant and the part of the plant used. The ethanolic extracts of Yemeni *T. terrestris* did not show antibacterial activity against bacteria tested whereas the methanolic/ethanolic extracts of different parts (fruits, roots and stems with leaves) of Iranian, Indian or Turkish *T. terrestris* inhibited the growth of different

microorganisms tested. [92] Antimicrobial activity of organic and aqueous extracts from fruits, leaves and roots of *T. terrestris* from Iraq was examined against 11 species of pathogenic and non-pathogenic microorganisms. All the extracts from the different parts of the plant showed antimicrobial activity against most tested microorganisms. The most active extract was ethanol extract from the fruits with a minimal inhibitory concentration of 0.15 mg/ml against different bacteria and fungi. [93]

Anti-cancerous activity:-

Among the different saponins analyzed from different parts (stem & fruit) of *T. terrestris* collected from different regions (Bulgaria, China & India), only spiro compounds exhibited remarkable anti cancerous activity. [94] The most active spirostanol glycoside (Hecogenin) exhibited a broad range of anticancer activity against cell lines SKMEL, KB, BT-549 and SKOV- 3. [95] Dioscin & also prosapogenin A of dioscin showed anti-cancerous activity against the cancer cell line K562 *in vitro*. [96]

Anthelmintic activity:-

Anthelmintic activity was observed only in the 50% methanol extracts of Indian *T. terrestris* (whole plant) using the nematode *Caenorhabditis elegans*. Further investigation revealed tribulosin and sitosterol glucoside as active components responsible for Anthelmintic activity. [97]

Miscellaneous uses:-

Lin *et al.*, investigated the use of *T. terrestris* fruits for treatment of vitiligo with

positive results. [98] The lyophilized saponin mixture of the plant caused a significant decrease on peristaltic movements of isolated sheep ureter and rabbit jejunum preparations and it was proposed that the saponin mixture may be useful for some smooth muscle spasms or colic pains. [99] The preventive and therapeutic effects of saponins from *T. terrestris* on diet induced hyperlipidemia in mice have been studied. It was showed that the saponins could lower the levels of serum TC, LDLc and liver TC, TG and increase the activities of superoxide-dismutase in liver. [100] Hypoglycemic effect of saponins from *T. terrestris* was investigated and the saponins were found to reduce the level of serum glucose significantly. [101]

***Rubia cordifolia* –**

In ayurvedic medicine, Manjistha (*Rubia cordifolia*) is a blood purifying herb. It cools and detoxifies the blood, removes stagnant blood, and dissolves obstructions in the blood flow. Manjistha also helps protect gums from receding. It is also believed to have astringent and anti-oxidant properties. Scientific studies have shown that it regulates blood pressure, blood vessel constriction, and helps protect from blood clot formation. Manjistha can also be used to treat uric acid and arthritis. Combined with other products, it can treat urinary infections, diarrhea, dysentery, and chronic fevers. Manjistha can be used to treat irregular menstruation. This herb can be used both internally and externally to bring luster to your skin and make it glow. Manjistha also helps removes pimples, freckles, other discolorations, and promotes the healing of skin tissues damaged by injury or infection.

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Antihyperglycemic, antistress and nootropic activity: Effect of alcoholic extract of roots of *Rubia cordifolia* was studied on elevated blood glucose level in alloxan treated animals. The extract reduced the blood sugar level raised by alloxan. Alcoholic extract enhanced brain gamma-amino-n-butyrac acid (GABA) levels and decreased brain dopamine and plasma corticosterone levels. Acidity and ulcers caused due to cold restraint stress were inhibited by alcoholic extract. . It also antagonized scopolamine induced learning and memory impairment. [102]

Anti-inflammatory activity: Extract of *Rubia cordifolia* in different solvents, is responsible for the inhibition of nitric oxide, a key mediator in the phenomenon of inflammation. Extract of

Rubia cordifolia contains effective antiinflammatory constituents therein to produce anti-inflammatory activity by inhibiting nitric oxide produced in vitro from sodium nitroprusside, and in LPS-activated murine peritoneal macrophages, ex vivo. [103]

Antibacterial activity: The chloroform and the methanol extract of *Rubia cordifolia* is responsible for its antibacterial activity specifically against towards the gram-positive strains, although gramnegative *P. aeruginosa* was also inhibited by the methanol extracts of plants in a dose dependent manner. The water extract of *Rubicordifolia* was significantly active against *B. subtilis* and *S. aureus* compared with streptomycin and penicillin G used as standards. [104]

Hepatoprotective Activity: Rubiadin, a major constituent isolated from *Rubia cordifolia* Linn., have hepatoprotective activity against carbon tetrachloride (CCl₄)-induced hepatic damage in rats. Rubiadin at a dose of 50, 100 and 200 mg/kg was administered orally once daily for 14 days. The substantially elevated serum enzymatic activities of serum glutamic oxaloacetic transaminase (SGOT), serum glutamate pyruvate transaminase (SGPT), serum alkaline phosphatase (SALP) and gamma-glutamyltransferase (gamma-GT) due to carbon tetrachloride treatment were dose dependently restored towards normalization. Meanwhile, the decreased activities of glutathione S-transferase and glutathione reductase were also restored towards normalization. [105]

Anticonvulsant Activity: A triterpene isolated from the acetone soluble part of petroleum ether extract of *R. cordifolia* was reported to have anticonvulsant activity. Triterpene inhibited seizures induced by maximum electric shock, electrical kindling, pentylenetetrazol and lithium-pilocarpine. Triterpene reduce locomotion as well as rearing. Brain GABA and 5-HT contents were raised by the compound. [106]

Antiviral Activity: Three naphthohydroquinones namely fuomollugin, mollugin and rubilactone isolated from the root of *Rubia cordifolia* are reported to have antiviral activity. Fuomollugin and mollugin strongly suppress the secretion of hepatitis B surface antigen, in human hepatoma Hep3B cells while having little effect on the viability of the cells. [107]

Radiation protection: The radioprotective potential of alcoholic extract of root of *R. cordifolia* was studied by survival, hemopoietic cell protection and micronucleus assay. A significant radiation protection (67%) as assessed by increased animal survival was observed when *R. cordifolia* (RC) extract was administered intraperitoneally, 90 min. before the radiation exposure. Besides, the extract also inhibited radiation induced lipid peroxidation measured by the inhibition of thiobarbituric acid reactive substance (TBARS). Thus, it appears that the alcoholic root extract of *R. cordifolia* provides significant protection against radiation induced lipid peroxidation, hemopoietic injury and genotoxicity. The mechanism of action of RC extract appears to be through its anti-oxidant, metal chelation and anti-inflammatory property. [108]

Asparagus racemosus –

Asparagus racemosus is a plant used in traditional Indian medicine (Ayurveda). The root is used to make medicine. Don't confuse *asparagus racemosus* with *Asparagus officinalis*, which is the type of asparagus that is commonly eaten as a vegetable. People use *asparagus racemosus* for upset stomach (dyspepsia), constipation, stomach spasms, and stomach ulcers. It is also used for fluid retention, pain, anxiety, cancer, diarrhea, bronchitis, tuberculosis, dementia, and diabetes. Some people use it to ease alcohol withdrawal. Women use *asparagus racemosus* for premenstrual syndrome (PMS) and uterine bleeding; and to start breast milk production. *Asparagus racemosus* is also used to increase sexual desire (as an aphrodisiac).

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Antidepressant activity:-

Methanolic extract of *Asparagus racemosus* significant antidepressant-like activity almost certainly by inhibiting MAO-A and MAO-B; and through interaction with adrenergic, dopaminergic, serotonergic and GABAergic systems. [109]

Antitussive activity:-

Methanolic extract of roots shatavari show significant antitussive activity on sulphur dioxide- induce cough in mice. The cough inhibition of 40% and 58.5%, respectively, was comparable to that of 10-20mg/kg of codeine phosphate observed 36% and 55.4%, respectively. [110]

Antisecretory activity:-

Asparagus racemosus causes an inhibitory effect on release of gastric hydrochloric acid

and protects gastric mucosal damage and found to be an effective antiulcerogenic agent. [111]

Adaptogenic activity:-

The aqueous extract of *Asparagus racemosus* reversed the effects of cisplatin on gastric emptying and also normalized cisplatin-induced intestinal hyper motility. [112]

Antidiarrhoeal and analgesic activity:-

Ethanol extract of whole plant *Asparagus racemosus* have Anti-diarrhoeal and Analgesic properties. In another study the effect of aqueous and ethanol extract of *Asparagus racemosus* for its antidiarrhoeal potential against experimental models of diarrhoea in Albino *Wistar* rats. [113]

Antiprotozoal activity:-

An aqueous solution of the crude alcoholic extract of the roots exhibited an inhibitory

effect of the growth of *Entamoeba histolytica*. [114]

Antibacterial activity:-

Methanol extract of the roots of *Asparagus racemosus* have antibacterial efficacy against *Escherichia coli*, *Shigella sonnei*, *Shigella dysenteriae*, *Shigella flexneri*, *Vibrio cholerae*, *Salmonella typhi*, *Salmonella typhimurium*, *Bacillus subtilis*, *Pseudomonas putida* and *Staphylococcus aureus* [115], and also show the spectrum of inhibition on *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Bacillus subtilis*, *Pseudomonas putida*, *Staphylococcus wernerii*, *Proteus mirabilis*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. [116]

Anti-inflammatory activity:-

Administration of 200 mg/kg (i.p.) leading to substantial reductions in skin thickness, tissue weight and also inflammatory cytokine production, neutrophil-mediated myeloperoxidase activity, and various histopathological indicators. Additionally Angiotensin converting enzyme have effective to reducing inflammatory damage induced by chronic TPA exposure and a significant inhibition of vascular permeability induced by acetic acid. [117]

Aphrodisiac activity:-

Lyophilized aqueous extracts roots of *A. racemosus* have sexual behavioral effects in male albino rats. Administrations of the aqueous extracts have pronounced anabolic effect in treated animals as evidenced by weight gains in body and reproductive organs. There was a significant variation in the sexual behavior of animals as reflected by reduction of mount latency, ejaculation latency, post ejaculatory latency, intromission latency. Penile erections are also considerably enhanced. Reduced hesitation time, also indicated an improvement in sexual behavior of extract treated animals. The observed effects appear to be the testosterone-like effects of the extracts. Nitric oxide based intervention may also be involved as observable from the improved penile erection. [118]

Anti-hepatocarcinogenesis:-

Histopathological study of hepatic tissues, treated with diethyl nitrosamine (DEN) and aqueous extract of the roots of *A. racemosus* prevented the incidence of hepatocarcinogenesis. [119]

Anti-stress activity:-

A. racemosus are used in Indian traditional medicine system for improving the general state of health and for stress-related immune disorders and these plants also beneficial in the management of stress and inflammatory conditions. The effects of the methanol and aqueous extracts of the tuberous roots of these plants were examined in an experimental mouse stress model. The extracts show an inhibitory effect on pro-inflammatory cytokines, namely interleukin 1β and tumor necrosis factor α , and on the production of nitric oxide in mouse macrophage cells RAW 264.7 stimulated by lipopolysaccharide in vitro. [120]

Conclusion

Plants, herbs, and ethnobotanicals have been used since the early days of humankind and are still used throughout the world for health promotion and treatment of disease. Plants and natural sources form the basis of today's modern medicine and contribute largely to the commercial drug preparations manufactured today. About 25% of drugs prescribed worldwide are derived from plants. Still, herbs, rather than drugs, are often used in health care. For some, herbal medicine is their preferred method of treatment. For others, herbs are used as adjunct therapy to conventional pharmaceuticals. However, in many developing societies, traditional medicine of which herbal medicine is a core part is the only system of health care available or affordable. Regardless of the reason, those using herbal medicines should be assured that the products they are buying are safe and contain what they are supposed to, whether this is a particular herb or a particular amount of a specific herbal component. Nutraceuticals, and analyte of interests are implemented safely in medicines

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with help of perfect study based on prior researches. Product of Renatus Nova was synthesized based on researches and findings from past hundred years of exploration nutraceuticals in chosen herbs, Also prevalence of researches has led to development of nano-materials, incorporating nanotechnology in therapeutics has been a major breakthrough , nano xanthenes have attained much popularity.

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